

Applicability of Kostanecki Robinson Reaction to Some O-Hydroxy diaryl diketones

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Synthesis of some dichromones has been described.

The Kostanecki Robinson reaction^{1,2} which consists in heating an orthohydroxy aryl ketone with an acid anhydride and sodium salt of the acid is known to produce chromones² or coumarins³ depending upon the nature of the ketones and experimental conditions.

Chakravarti and Sarkar⁴ have shown that some orthohydroxy diaryl diketones on being treated with acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate produce dichromones having physiological activity.

The present work is an extension of the Kostanecki Robinson reaction already taken up by Chakravarti *et al.* in this laboratory on diketones⁵ (I) to give dichromone derivatives of the structures (II).

Ia, R = H

Ib, R = Cl

IIa, R = H

IIb, R = Cl

The acetoxy dichromones (II) on hydrolysis with 60% sulphuric acid at 50–60° produce the corresponding hydroxy derivatives.

1. M. Blumberg and S. Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2191.
2. W. Baker and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1981.
3. R. W. Cantor, A. R. Martin and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1877.
4. D. Chakravarti and U. Sarkar, *Science and Culture*, 1966, **32**, 592.
5. D. Chakravarti, N. N. Chakravarti and S. Samanta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 457.

It is anticipated that such compounds with two hydroxy chromone nuclei bridged by a methylene group may be of importance in the biochemical field. The structures of the compounds have been suggested from a study of the IR spectra of the diacetoxy and dihydroxy chromones (given under experimental). The possibility of the compounds being the tetraacetates of the diketones (I) was eliminated by the preparation of the tetraacetates by heating the diketones with acetic anhydride and pyridine and direct comparison with the above products. The homogeneity of the compounds was established by T.L.C.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 3,3'-methylene bis-(7-acetoxy-2-methyl chromone) (IIa). A mixture of the diketone, 1,5-bis[2,4-dihydroxy phenyl] pentan-1,5-dione⁵ (Ia) (4 g.), acetic anhydride (40 ml) and freshly fused sodium acetate (9 g) was taken in a round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser protected by a calcium chloride guard tube and heated at 140° for two hours in an oil bath. The temperature was then gradually allowed to rise to 180° in the course of about two hours and heating was continued for another four hours at this temperature. During heating 4-5 ml of acetic anhydride was added at an interval of two hours. The reaction mixture on cooling to 100° was poured in ice-water with vigorous stirring and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The resulting brown coloured residue was filtered, treated with a few ml. of methanol and crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, m.p. 264°. Yield 1.4 g. Found : C, 66.72; H, 4.18; C₂₅H₂₀O₈ requires; C, 66.96; H, 4.46%.

The compound was homogeneous by T.L.C (R_f 0.5) using chloroform as developer.

3,3'-methylene bis-(7-hydroxy-2-methyl chromone): The above diacetoxy compound (IIa), (1 g.) was suspended in 60% sulphuric acid (50 ml) and heated at 50-60° for about an hour. The reaction mixture on cooling was diluted with water and the deposited solid was filtered off. The crude product was purified by dissolution through 2% cold caustic soda solution and acidification. Finally the residue was repeatedly crystallised from diethylene glycol, m.p. > 320°. Yield 0.5 g. Found : C, 68.86; H, 4.05; C₂₁H₁₆O₆ requires, C, 69.23; H, 4.4%. IR spectrum (Nujol) : γ_{max} 3333 cm⁻¹ (phenolic -OH, 1634 cm⁻¹) (γ -pyronyl > c = O), 1567, 1497 cm⁻¹ (aromatic vibration).

Preparation of the tetra acetate of the diketone (Ia): The diketone (0.5g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (2 ml.) and acetic anhydride (3 ml.) was added. The mixture was heated on a water bath for four hours and poured in ice water. The crude solid was filtered, washed with dil. caustic soda solution and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 93°. The compound developed no coloration with ferric chloride solution. Found : C, 62.23; H, 5.14; C₂₅H₂₄O₁₀ requires, C, 61.98; H, 4.95%.

Preparation of 3,3'-methylene bis-(7-acetoxy-6-chloro-2-methyl chromone) (IIb): A mixture of the diketone 1,5-bis[2,4-dihydroxy-5-chloro phenyl]-pentane 1,5- dione⁵ (4 g.); acetic anhydride (40 ml) and fused sodium acetate (9 g) was similarly treated as in the case of (IIa). The product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 292°. Yield 1.6 g. Found : C, 58.43; H, 3.70; C₂₅H₁₈O₈Cl₂ requires, C, 58.02; H, 3.48%.

IR spectrum (Nujol) γ_{max} : 1770 cm⁻¹ and 1250 cm⁻¹ (acetoxy group), 1640 cm⁻¹ (γ -pyronyl > c = o) 1613 and 1563 cm⁻¹ (phenyl nucleus).

The pure compound gave a single spot on T.L.C. (R_f 0.6) using 3% methanol and chloroform as developer.

3-3'-methylene bis-[7-hydroxy-6-chloro-2-methyl chromone]: The above diacetate of dichromone (IIb) (1 g) was similarly hydrolysed with 60% sulphuric acid as in the case of (IIa), m.p. $> 340^\circ$ (diethylene glycol). Yield 0.49 g. Found : C, 57.62; H, 4.00; $C_{21}H_{14}O_6Cl_2$ requires; C, 58.2; H, 3.23%.

Preparation of tetraacetate of diketone (Ib) : The diketone (Ib) was dissolved in pyridine and heated with acetic anhydride for four hours. The solid formed on pouring the reaction mixture to ice water was purified by washing with 3% NaOH solution. The alkali insoluble residue was purified through chromatography over silica gel and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 144° . Found : C, 54.75; H, 4.63; $C_{25}H_{22}O_{10}Cl_2$ requires, C, 54.24; H, 3.97%.

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